

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

AETIOLOGICAL AGENTS FOR PULMONARY EXACERBATIONS IN CHILDREN WITH CYSTIC FIBROSIS: AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY IN FAUJI FOUNDATION HOSPITAL RAWALPINDI PAKISTAN

¹Dr Fatima Naz Awan, ²Dr Tania Saif, ³Dr Maria Tariq

¹Foundation University Medical College, Fatimaawan1329@gmail.com

²Foundation University Medical College, tania.raja95@gmail.com

³Foundation University Medical College, tariqmaria67@gmail.com

Article Received: August 2020 **Accepted:** September 2020 **Published:** October 2020

Abstract:

Background- In cystic fibrosis the main cause of mortality and morbidity is pulmonary disease. Normally with particular pattern of bacterial pathogens which depend upon age, this infection occurs.

Objective- The goal of this study is to determine the aetiological agents with cystic fibrosis in children for pulmonary exacerbations and find out its relationship with demographic variables.

Method- This study is based on observations for these 104 children were selected with cystic fibrosis with pulmonary exacerbations and they all tested by using proper laboratory techniques for viral pathogens, mycobacteria, fungi and bacteria. With demographic variables isolation frequency of different organisms were associated and calculated.

Results- Out of all selected children 29% i.e. 27 children were isolated in viral RNA, 35% i.e. 37 were isolated with bacteria. In 29.8% i.e. 31 children the growth of most common *Pseudomonas* bacteria was found while in 3 i.e. 2.9% isolated for *Burkholderia cepacia* complex (Bcc) was found. The most common virus among all virus was Rhinovirus and this was found in 17.4% i.e. 16 patients while in 4 i.e. 4.3% coronavirus was identified. Mycobacteria and fungi were isolated from 4 (3.7%) and 23 (22%) children respectively. The most common fungus found was *Aspergillus flavus* from 12.5% i.e. in 13 children.

Conclusion- During exacerbation *Pseudomonas* was found as most common organism. Infection with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and Bcc was observed whereas infection with tuberculous mycobacteria was not observed. In CF morbidity *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and Bcc have a role. However, severe exacerbations had association with polymicrobial.

Keywords: Polymicrobial infection, *Pseudomonas*, microbiology, cystic fibrosis, children, acute exacerbation

Corresponding author:

Dr Fatima Naz Awan,

Foundation University Medical College, Fatimaawan1329@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Fatima Naz Awan et al, *Aetiological Agents For Pulmonary Exacerbations In Children With Cystic Fibrosis: An Observational Study In Fauji Foundation Hospital Rawalpindi Pakistan.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(10).

INTRODUCTION:

One of a common inherited life-limiting disease is Cystic fibrosis. In Pakistani population the prevalence of Cystic fibrosis is not known. In cystic fibrosis the main cause of morbidity is pulmonary involvement. When pulmonary disease gets worse at acute level then it is called exacerbations. There is no resemblance of aetiological agents which cause pneumonia and pulmonary exacerbation. There are more chances of acquiring fungal, viral, mycobacterial infection for a child with cystic fibrosis. In cystic fibrosis the main cause of mortality and morbidity is pulmonary disease. Normally with particular pattern of bacterial pathogens which depend upon age, this infection occurs. The goal of this study is to determine the aetiological agents with cystic fibrosis in children for pulmonary exacerbations and find out its relationship with demographic variables. In 80% patients with cystic fibrosis *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was one of the most commonly isolated during exacerbation. With CF, *Bcc* is also unique organism. This infection can be eradicated with appropriate early and aggressive antibiotics, however in most of the cases if not eradicated completely then antibiotics can be helpful in delaying progression of pulmonary disease, degree of inflammation can be reduced and colonization can be prevented. The serious concern in CF is non-tuberculous mycobacteria. Various factors like steroid treatment, CF related diabetes, malnutrition and severity of illness dispose children in mycobacterial infection.

METHOD:

This study is based on observations, which completed

over 18 months. For this study 104 children were selected with cystic fibrosis with pulmonary exacerbations and they all tested by using proper laboratory techniques for viral pathogens, mycobacteria, fungi and bacteria. A written consent papers was signed by parents of all the selected children. Respiratory specimens of throat swabs, nasopharyngeal aspirates, induced or expectorated sputum were collected from selected 104 children. Those children were selected who were up to 18 years old presented for pulmonary exacerbation and those were excluded who had a previous record of exacerbation within six months.

In microbiology laboratory samples were sent to detect the viral RNA, mycobacterial culture, fungal and bacterial infection. For Gram stain bacterial isolation samples were tarnished and also immunized on *B. cepacia* Selective Agar, chocolate, blood and MacConkey. For fungus identification, samples were also mounted on 10% Sabouraud dextrose agar and potassium hydroxide. With demographic variables isolation frequency of different organisms were associated and calculated. Using McNemar's test proportional difference between each pathogen was assessed.

RESULTS:

Out of 104 selected patients 33 was females and 71 were males. The mean age of appearing illness was 2.0 ± 1.1 years while 4.2 ± 1.8 years was at the time of diagnosis. In all selected patients, 63 were outpatients while 41 was in patients. Out of all selected children 29% i.e. 27 children were isolated in viral RNA, 35% i.e. 37 were isolated with bacteria.

Table I. Summary of microbial pathogens demonstrated in respiratory tract secretions of children with cystic fibrosis and pulmonary exacerbations

Organisms	Positive (%)	Remarks
Bacteria		
Total positive	37	-
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	31 (29.8)	-
<i>Burkholderia cepacia</i>	3 (2.8)	-
<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	2 (1.9)	-
<i>Acinetobacter</i> spp.	1 (0.9)	-
Fungi		
Total positive	23	-
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	13 (12.5)	-
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	5 (4.5)	-
<i>Candida albicans</i>	4 (3.8)	-
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	1 (0.9)	-

In 29.8% i.e. 31 children the growth of most common *Pseudomonas* bacteria was found while in 3 i.e. 2.9% isolated for *Burkholderia cepacia* complex (Bcc) was found. The most common virus among all virus was Rhinovirus and this was found in 17.4% i.e. 16 patients while in 4 i.e. 4.3% coronavirus was identified. Mycobacteria and fungi were isolated from 4 (3.7%) and 23 (22%) children respectively. The most common fungus found was *Aspergillus flavus* from 12.5% i.e. in 13 children.

Table II. Comparison of clinical variables of children who had grown various microorganisms and children who had not

Characteristics	Bacteria		Fungi		Mycobacteria		Viruses	
	Grown isolated (n=37)	Not grown (n=27)	Grown (n=67)	Not grown (n=65)	Grown (n=23)	Not grown (n=81)	Isolated (n=4)	Not (n=100)
Age (yr) (mean±SD)	9.9±5.5	10.4±5.5	10.6±5.5	10.1±5.5	12.6±5.8	10.1±5.5	9.1±6.2	10.8±5.3
Sex								
Male, n (%)	18 (48.6)*	52 (77)	17 (73.9)	54 (66.6)	4 (100)*	67 (67)	18 (66.6)	46 (70.7)
Female, n (%)	19 (51.4)*	15 (23)	6 (26.1)	27 (33.4)	0 (0)*	33 (33)	9 (33.3)	19 (29.3)
Age at onset of illness (yr) (mean±SD)	1.2±0.8	1.8±1.1	0.8±0.8	1.1±1.4	1.3±1.8	1.0±1.3	1.0±1.3	1.0±1.4
Age at diagnosis (yr) (mean±SD)	3.6±3.3	3.8±3.2	4.3±3.2	3.5±3.3	3.7±3.3	3.5±3.3	3.1±3.2	3.8±3.2
Treated as								
Inpatient, n (%)	24 (64.8)	16 (23.8)	10 (43.4)	31 (38.2)	2 (50)*	39 (39)	10 (37)	23 (35.3)
Outpatient, n (%)	13 (35.2)	51 (76.2)	13 (56.6)	50 (61.8)	2 (50)*	61 (61)	17 (63)	42 (64.7)

DISCUSSION:

In cystic fibrosis the main cause of morbidity is pulmonary involvement. When pulmonary disease gets worse at acute level then it is called exacerbations. There is no resemblance of aetiological agents which cause pneumonia and pulmonary exacerbation. There are more chances of acquiring fungal, viral, mycobacterial infection for a child with cystic fibrosis. In cystic fibrosis the main cause of mortality and morbidity is pulmonary disease. Normally with pattern of bacterial pathogens which depend upon age, this infection occurs. In 80% patients with cystic fibrosis *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was one of the most isolated during exacerbation. In any event one of the microbial operators was distinguished in 68 youngsters (65.3%). In concentrates from different pieces of the world, *Pseudomonas* was the transcendent bacteria¹⁵⁻¹⁸. The level of kids who developed *Pseudomonas* in our investigation was 29.8 percent, which was lesser than the consequences of an examination (36%) from Brazil¹⁵ and (40%) Italy¹⁶. In a review study Razvi *et al* [19] detailed a critical decrease in the yearly commonness of *Pseudomonas* from 60.4 percent in 1995 to 56.1 percent in 2005 ($P < 0.001$). In a prior investigation on 120 CF kids between 1995 to 2002 at our middle, *Pseudomonas* was archived in 42 for every cent¹¹, which has declined to 29.8 percent in 2015 in the current examination. Potential clarifications incorporate expanded mindfulness about disease control techniques, utilization of long-haul immunosuppressive treatment with azithromycin and judicious utilization of antimicrobials for early destruction of *P. aeruginosa*.

Hospitalized care was needed in all the kids who had co-contamination proposing expanded severity of intensifications in these patients. Our investigation has repeated the part of non-bacterial microorganisms causing pneumonic intensifications in youngsters with CF.

CONCLUSION:

During exacerbation *Pseudomonas* was found as most common organism. Infection with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and Bcc was observed whereas infection with tuberculous mycobacteria was not observed. In CF morbidity *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and Bcc have a role. However, severe exacerbations had association with polymicrobial.

REFERENCES:

1. Mehta S, Wadhwa UN, Mehta SK, Chhuttani PN. Fibrocystic disease of pancreas in India. *Indian Pediatr* 1968; 5 : 185-91.
2. Kapoor V, Shastri SS, Kabra M, Kabra SK, Ramachandran V, Arora S, *et al*. Carrier frequency of F508del mutation of cystic fibrosis in Indian population. *J Cyst Fibros* 2006; 5 : 43-6.
3. Filkins LM, O'Toole GA. Cystic fibrosis lung infections: Polymicrobial, complex, and hard to treat. *PLoS Pathog* 2015 31; 11 : e1005258.
4. Coburn B, Wang PW, Diaz Caballero J, Clark ST, Brahma V, Donaldson S, *et al*. Lung microbiota across age and disease stage in cystic fibrosis. *Sci Rep* 2015; 5 : 10241.
5. Folescu TW, da Costa CH, Cohen RWF, Neto OC da C, Albano RM, Marques EA. *Burkholderia cepacia* complex: Clinical course in cystic fibrosis patients. *BMC Pulm Med* 2015; 15 : 158.
6. Ranganathan SC, Hall GL, Sly PD, Stick SM, Douglas TA. Early lung disease in infants and preschool children with cystic fibrosis. What have we learned and what should we do about it? *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2017; 195 : 1567-75.
7. Olivier KN, Weber DJ, Wallace RJ Jr, Faiz AR, Lee JH, Zhang Y, *et al*. Nontuberculous mycobacteria. I: Multicenter prevalence study in cystic fibrosis. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2003; 167 : 828-34.
8. Gulla KM, Balaji A, Mukherjee A, Jat KR, Sankar J, Lodha R, *et al*. Course of illness after viral infection in Indian children with cystic fibrosis. *J Trop Pediatrics* 2019; 65 : 176-82.
9. Wang JH, Kwon HJ, Jang YJ. Rhinovirus enhances various bacterial adhesions to nasal epithelial cells simultaneously. *Laryngoscope* 2009; 119 : 1406-11.
10. Güngör O, Tamay Z, Güler N, Erturan Z. Frequency of fungi in respiratory samples from Turkish cystic fibrosis patients. *Mycoses* 2013; 56 : 123-9.
11. Kabra SK, Kabra M, Lodha R, Shastri S. Cystic fibrosis in India. *Pediatr Pulmonol* 2007; 42 : 1087-94.
12. Fuchs HJ, Borowitz DS, Christiansen DH, Morris EM, Nash ML, Ramsey BW, *et al*. Effect of aerosolized recombinant human DNase on exacerbations of respiratory symptoms and on pulmonary function in patients with cystic fibrosis. The pulmozyme study group. *N Engl J*

- Med* 1994; 331 : 637-42.
13. Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute. *Performance standards for antimicrobial susceptibility testing; 24th informational supplement*. CLSI Document M100-S24. Wayne, PA: CLSI; 2014. p. 230.
 14. De Bel A, De Geyter D, De Schutter I, Mouton C, Wellemans I, Hanssens L, et al. Sampling and decontamination method for culture of nontuberculous mycobacteria in respiratory samples of cystic fibrosis patients. *J Clin Microbiol* 2013; 51 : 4204-6.
 15. Santana MA, Matos E, do Socorro Fontoura M, Franco R, Barreto D, Lemos AC. Prevalence of pathogens in cystic fibrosis patients in Bahia, Brazil. *Braz J Infect Dis* 2003; 7 : 69-72.
 16. Lambiase A, Raia V, Del Pezzo M, Sepe A, Carnovale V, Rossano F. Microbiology of airway disease in a cohort of patients with cystic fibrosis. *BMC Infect Dis* 2006; 6 : 4.
 17. Quintas S, Pereira L, Lito L, Barreto C. Epidemiological survey of bacteria isolated from the respiratory tract of cystic fibrosis patients. *Rev Port Pneumol* 2003; 9 : 337-52.
 18. Muñoz C, Juncosa T, Gené A, Fortea J, Sécui JL, Latorre C. Microbiological study of the respiratory tract in children with cystic fibrosis. *Enferm Infecc Microbiol Clin* 1996; 14 : 142-4.
 19. Razvi S, Quittell L, Sewall A, Quinton H, Marshall B, Saiman L. Respiratory microbiology of patients with cystic fibrosis in the United States, 1995 to 2005. *Chest* 2009; 136 : 1554-60.
 20. Whiteford ML, Wilkinson JD, McColl JH, Conlon FM, Michie JR, Evans TJ, et al. Outcome of *Burkholderia (Pseudomonas) cepacia* colonisation in children with cystic fibrosis following a hospital outbreak. *Thorax* 1995; 50 : 1194-8.